

Book Series Review

Süverdem, F., B., & Tekalp, S. (2022). *Linguistics: Cross-cultural perspectives* (Vol. 1). Peter Lang Verlag. 10.3726/b20598

Sancaktaroğlu Bozkurt, S., Taşdan Doğan, T., E. (2022). *Translation Studies: Translating in the 21st century – Multiple identities* (Vol. 2). Peter Lang Verlag. 10.3726/b20596

Karaduman, A., & Öztürk, G. (2022). *Literature: Different perspectives and approaches in postcolonial studies* (Vol. 3). Peter Lang Verlag. 10.3726/b20597

Göksel ÖZTÜRK¹

¹ Asst. Prof., Department of Translation and Interpreting, Faculty of Humanities, Bursa Technical University, Türkiye, gokseledu@gmail.com, ORCID ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-5883-3211

Synergy: Translation Studies, Literature, Linguistics is a series of books that appears in three volumes. The series editors are Aslı Özlem Tarakcioğlu, A.Nejat Töngür, and Ayşe Selmin Söylemez. The first of the series was published in 2022. It is apparent that fresh understandings for readers are in the spirit of the *Synergy* book series. The three volumes seek to offer fresh viewpoints to their disciplines from diverse aspects.

The first volume of the series, *Linguistics Cross-Cultural Perspectives*, is edited by F. Büşra Süverdem and Selen Tekalp. The edited volume consists of 233 pages and 10 chapters. Following an outline of the scope of the volume, a short description of the chapters is presented in the introduction. The chapters are written by experts and researchers offering a thought-provoking read for readers. The book provides diverse perspectives from various linguistic domains encouraging readers to explore new understandings. The topics covered by the authors of chapters in the book include, but are not limited to critical discourse analysis, corpus-based crosslinguistic investigation, cultural aspects of language learning, intercultural pragmatics contrastive studies in applied linguistics, and cross-cultural communication. There is no doubt that the book primarily focuses on the cross-cultural dimensions of language by greatly enriching the literature in the field. To be more precise, Chapter 1, by Ahmet Bora Dindar and Zeynep Doyuran, is in search of learning the creation of hegemony as well as finding sociocultural and historical settings designation of discourse examining Yaşar Kemal's *İnce Memed I*. The following chapter, by Alper Kumcu, presents a corpus-based, crosslinguistic investigation in which he looks into the weight of moving-time and moving-ego patterns in

Turkish. As the author suggests time is an essential aspect of our lived experience and a vital component of human cognition, so the subject provides a thought-provoking read. Chapter 3, by Betül Ertek, construes cultural aspects of language learning and the interdependent relationship between the concepts of culture and language in the learning process. The following chapter, by Canan Terzi, examines the forms of address pre-service English-language teachers prefer to use in academic and non-academic settings and investigates how appropriate the address forms preferred by pre-service English-language teachers are according to native speakers of English. Chapter 5, by Emel Kökpınar Kaya, invites readers to explore the newsprint media representations of Türkiye's role in the refugee crisis particularly following the Taliban takeover in Afghanistan by setting out discursive strategies and linguistic means depicted in a newspaper. The next chapter, by Emin Yaş, encourages readers to explore the aspects of the monitor theory in second-language acquisition. Chapter 7, by Hacer Hande Uysal and Sami Alhasnawi, enriches readers with a comprehensive critical review of contrastive studies in applied linguistics as well as a macro-focus on language analysis. In the following chapter, by Mustafa Sarıoğlu, the effect of lexical aspects on Turkish EFL learners' use of present perfect forms is examined. Chapter 9, by Müge Gündüz, investigates understanding the experiences of international students as they grapple with the challenges and opportunities presented by conflicting norms and values. The last chapter, by Sladjana Djordjevic, looks into the influence of linguistic mediation on communicative behavior and early second-language appropriation and provides qualitative analyses' results of the interactions.

The second volume, *Translation Studies: Translating in the 21st Century-Multiple Identities*, is edited by Sinem Sancaktaroğlu-Bozkurt and Tuğçe Elif Taşdan-Doğan. The book is 236 pages long and comprises 12 chapters written by valuable voices in the field of translation studies in line with interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches. After providing an overview of the volume's scope, the introduction presents a summary of the chapters. Authored by experts and researchers, these chapters offer an engaging read for the readers. The book offering various contemporary subjects encourages readers to discover a diverse and vibrant array of topics in translation studies. The topics covered by the authors of chapters in the book include but are not limited to training of sign language interpreters, translation of sound books for children and comic strips in multimodal perspectives, remaking repertoire, translation of linguistic hybridity, (self-)investigation of translation, manga translation, translation memories in the legal translation process, poetry translation through common machine translation tools, translation education, translation of an alien language, identity of translators. The first chapter, by Ayşe Şirin Okyayuz and Hilal Erkazancı Durmuş, illustrates the interconnectedness of identity formation, deaf sports, and sign language interpreting in consideration of a sociological perspective. Besides, the authors propose a training model for sign language interpreting aiming to establish a professional habitus that

encompasses the attitudes and abilities that SLIs are expected to develop through socialization and professional education. The following chapter, by Gökçen Hastürkoğlu, looks into translation problems regarding sound elements in a multimodal children's work and reveals the solutions translation finds to provide the meaning both at semantic and cognitive levels. Chapter 3, by Göksel Öztürk, analyses comic strips in a multimodal framework as well as questioning the visibility of translators in translation of a comic strip series. The following chapter, by Mehmet Erguvan, focuses on how TV shows from different cultures are remade for the Turkish audience, a common type of audiovisual translation in Türkiye, and examines the portrayal of LGBTI+ characters in those remakes. Chapter 5, by Selen Tekalp, invites readers to a thought-provoking read by exploring hybridity in a translated postcolonial literary work. Employing the hybrid elements, Tekalp encourages readers to think about recolonization and decolonization concepts. The following chapter, by Sema Üstün Külünk, uptraces the self-portrayal of a translator's identity and questions translatorial identity. The next chapter, by Yeşim Dinçkan, looks into the use of sensitive language in Manga translation. Intending to find translators' choices, Dinçkan uses content, linguistic track, and visual track dimensions in the analysis of three translated mangas. Chapter 8, by Büşra Özer Erdoğan, elaborates strengths and weaknesses of translation memories in the legal process, which is also a call for further research regarding translation memory use in legal translation. The following chapter, by Kadir Sariaslan, explores the enjambments analysis in two translated poems: *The Waste Land* and *Seyfi Baba*. The translations of Google, Yandex, Bing, and human, as a reference, are compared employing a quality assessment metric. Chapter 10, by Müge Kalıpçı, discusses perceptions of language and literature students and their attitudes towards translation courses provided at universities. The following chapter, Siray Lengerli Aydemir, focuses on the positioning of human language as a hyperobject while translating an alien language. Aydemir analyses the translation of a Hollywood movie in terms of positioning human language in communication, (mis)interpretation, and action. The last chapter, by Ahsen Ay and Elif Ceylan Yağız, examines the depiction of characters who are translators and play lead roles in three 21st-century films. Drawing from both textual and visual elements of these films, the study analyses the identity, status, role, and image of these translator characters as portrayed in the cinematic discourse.

The third volume, *Synergy Literature: Different Perspectives and Approaches in Postcolonial Studies* is edited by Alev Karaduman and Göksel Öztürk. The book is 205 pages long and comprises 12 chapters written by a group of qualified academics in the field given interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches. Following the introduction part in which an overview of the volume's scope is given the summaries of chapters are also provided. In the spirit of the *Synergy* book series, the book offers an interesting and captivating experience for the readers. Besides, it provides a stimulating collection of contemporary subjects. The topics covered by the authors of chapters in the book include but are not limited to postcolonial

reading, feminist activism, postcolonial translation, postcolonial gothic, colonial biopolitics, volunteerism, and presentations of masculinity and femininity. The first chapter, by A. Nejat Töngür, invites readers to explore transcultural encounters and relationships with many people from different countries including his friends, his benefactors, his slaves, and Friday from a postcolonial hermeneutical perspective in the novel *Robinson Crusoe*. The following chapter, by Alev Karaduman, intriguingly depicts the post-colonial conflicts between history and identity in Okot p'Bitek's *Song of Lawino*. Chapter 3, by Kuğu Tekin and Zeynep Rana Turgut, investigates the black feminism in Bernardine Evaristo's novel, *Girl, Woman, Other* by analyzing twelve mostly black women characters. The next chapter, by Sinem Sancaktaroğlu Bozkurt, encourages readers to explore the concept of translation within postcolonial translation studies, with a particular focus on Abdulrazak Gurnah's novels that have been translated into Turkish. His novels and their Turkish translations are comparatively examined by applying the concepts of "cultural translation" and "translated men". Chapter 5, by Yıldırım Çevik, represents the gothic elements and the postcolonial under the background of slavery in Toni Morrison's *Beloved*. The following chapter, by Pınar Taşdelen, examines the dichotomy between the past living in the memory of the immigrants and the uncertain future that is built on their present anxieties in Carol Ann Duffy's selected poems. Chapter 7, by İmren Yelmiş, encourages readers to discuss the biopolitical representation of the British colonial administration in the Great Famine. The following chapter, by Emine Seda Çağlayan Mazanoğlu, explores racism against immigrants and the thin and dangerous boundary between nationalism and racism. Chapter 9, by Zafer Parlak, dwells on postcolonial perspectives of Voluntary Service Overseas. The next chapter, by Azime Ekşen Yakar, examines how Zadie Smith's *The Wife of Willesden*, a modern adaptation of Chaucer's *The Wife of Bath's Tale*, challenges the oppressive forces that marginalize women and minorities in English literature and reveals the struggle for power between the colonizer and the colonized using postcolonial theories of rewriting. Chapter 11, by Yakut Akbay, investigates subversion and containment in Rudyard Kipling's *Kim* applying a New Historicist analysis. The last chapter by, Duygu Serdaroğlu, explores the diverse and dynamic expressions of femininity and masculinity in Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Buchi Emecheta's *The Bride Price*, and reveals how these novels critique and reshape the cultural and gendered structures of their colonized male-dominated culture.